

Socioeconomic Metrics for the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework

Deliverable 5.2.

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Summary

D5.2. offers a preliminary proposal of socioeconomic metrics for assessing the status of the B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LL) towards a ‘water-smart society’. This deliverable is a result from Task 5.2. – Analysis of drivers and barriers for implementation and acceptance of water-smart solutions of Work Package 5 of B-WaterSmart - Society, Governance, Policy. Part of this task involves providing inputs to the ongoing work of WP6 – Water-smartness assessment framework (task 6.2).

According to the architecture set for the assessment framework, the metrics herein proposed are aligned with specific assessment criteria, which derive from the B-WaterSmart definition of a water-smart society (see section 2) and from the strategic objectives (SO) defined for the six LL of the project: Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon and Venice.

We start by explaining the methodology followed to identify the metrics proposed by WP5 (section 2). Section 3 includes a discussion of the metrics proposed. This is meant to serve as a supporting guide to read and interpret the metrics list, which is compiled in Annex 2. Section 4 sums up the key challenges and recommendations across the dimensions of society, governance and policy, towards a framework that can best support the implementation of a water-smart society and circular economy (CE), in Europe and beyond.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AC	Assessment Criteria
CE	Circular Economy
CICES	Common Classification of Ecosystem Services
COP	Communities of Practice
ESS	Ecosystem services
GCF	Governance Capacity Framework
GPP	Green Public Procurement
LL	Living Labs
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SO	Strategic Objectives
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

D5.2. offers a preliminary proposal of socioeconomic metrics for assessing the status of the B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LL) towards a 'water-smart society', where societal well-being is generated via the sustainable management of water resources. These metrics help to assess the performance of not only the partners of B-WaterSmart towards achieving the project goals, but also encompass an evaluation of the performance of cities and regions at the scale of the LL.

This deliverable is a result from Task 5.2. – Analysis of drivers and barriers for implementation and acceptance of water-smart solutions of Work Package (WP) 5 of B-WaterSmart - Society, Governance, Policy. Part of this task involves providing inputs to the ongoing work of WP6 – Water-smartness assessment framework (task 6.2).

According to the structure set for the assessment framework, the metrics herein proposed are aligned with specific assessment criteria (AC), which are derived from the B-WaterSmart definition of a water-smart society (see section 2, Methodology) and from the strategic objectives (SO) defined for the six LL of the project: Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon and Venice.

We start by explaining the methodology followed to identify the metrics proposed by WP5 (section 2). Section 3 includes a review of each of the selected AC, as well as a discussion of the metrics proposed. This is meant to serve as a supporting guide to read and interpret the metrics list, which is compiled in Annex 2. The file includes a set of categories proposed by WP5 which will facilitate the hierarchisation and LL's decisions about their approach to the assessment framework. This is expected to support the stage of validation from December 2021. Finally, section 4 sums up the key challenges and recommendations across the dimensions of society, governance and policy, towards a framework that can best support the implementation of a water-smart society and circular economy (CE), in Europe and beyond.

In order to facilitate the use of this report as a guide for interpreting the preliminary list of metrics proposed, SO, AC and metrics and numbered accordingly to the table of Annex 2.

1. Introduction

D5.2. offers a preliminary proposal of socioeconomic metrics for assessing the status of the B-WaterSmart Living Labs (LL) towards a 'water-smart society'. This deliverable is a result from Task 5.2. – Analysis of drivers and barriers for implementation and acceptance of water-smart solutions of Work Package 5 of B-WaterSmart - Society, Governance, Policy. Part of this task involves providing inputs to the ongoing work of WP6 – Water-smartness assessment framework (task 6.2).

According to the architecture set for the assessment framework, the metrics herein proposed are aligned with specific assessment criteria (AC), which derive from the B-WaterSmart definition of a water-smart society and from the strategic objectives (SO) defined for the six LL of the project: Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon and Venice. The definition of a **water-smart society** has been co-developed with the LL in a series of workshops, with consultation of the different WPs of the Project. It is currently as follows:

*Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in **continuous co-learning and innovation (SO E)** to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure **water for all relevant uses (SO A)**, to **safeguard ecosystems and their services to society (SO B)**, to **boost value creation around water (SO C)**, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure (SO D).*

At this early stage of development, the WP5 team has concentrated their inputs and recommendations on those SO most directly related to the social and governance dimensions of the framework (in bold in the definition above):

A – Ensuring water for all relevant uses

B - Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society

C - Boosting value creation around water

E - Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation

A set of AC has been co-developed for each SO, and discussed with the LL representatives through a series of online workshops organised by WP6. For the purposes of this D5.2 report, we have considered the updated version that resulted from the workshop held on the 29th of September 2021.

Along with D5.2, also WP2 and WP4 are submitting their contributions to the assessment framework, which will be discussed and validated with the LL representatives from December 2021. As there are multiple AC that are simultaneously relevant for different WPs and fields of analysis, these multiple contributions will have to be later combined and consolidated, in order to clear up any redundancies and refine the set of indicators. This will be an iterative and interactive process that will be further co-developed and consolidated throughout the project, until Month 30 (February 2023).

In this light, the current WP5 report is to be understood as a very preliminary draft that aims at starting and facilitating a discussion of the assessment framework within the project and with the LL, a first stepping stone. The ultimate goal is to set up a framework that is robust, consistent, responds directly to the SO defined by the B-WaterSmart LLs and allows for a reliable and encompassing monitoring over the long term and beyond the duration of the project (2020-2024). The set of indicators will be accessible through a digital tool (water-smartness dashboard) being developed by the project partners under Task 3.9.

The social and governance dimensions raise challenges in terms of data accessibility, new emerging concepts and social dynamics, including recent changes in policy, political and economic circumstances. Furthermore, there are developments in the social sciences and empirical research (e.g. concerning social justice) that ought to be covered in order to assess the evolution of a water-smart society. In this report, we have sought to identify these key challenges and offer recommendations on how to address them, taking into account the state of the art in policy and research on water innovation.

We start by explaining the methodology followed to identify the metrics proposed by WP5 (section 2). Section 3 includes a review of each of the selected AC, as well as a discussion of the metrics proposed. This is meant to serve as a supporting guide to read and interpret the metrics list, which is compiled in Annex 2. The file includes a set of categories proposed by WP5 which will facilitate the hierarchisation and LL's decisions about their approach to the assessment framework. This is expected to support the stage of validation from December 2021. Finally, section 4 sums up the key challenges and recommendations across the dimensions of society, governance and policy, towards a framework that can best support the implementation of a water-smart society and circular economy (CE), in Europe and beyond.

In order to facilitate the use of this report as a guide for interpreting the preliminary list of metrics proposed, SO, AC and metrics and numbered accordingly to the table of Annex 2.

2. Methodology

The development of the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework follows an interactive and iterative process continued until Month 30 of the project, under the coordination of WP6. It started within WP6 by co-creating the above definition of a water-smart society amongst the partners, which reflects the strategic agenda of the project, as well as the specificities of each LL (in bold the dimensions covered by D5.2).

From here, a list of SO was discussed and refined with the LLs, aligned with their strategic agendas, as well as a set of AC, which constitute the key nodes of the assessment framework and inform the identification of metrics (two to five per each criterion), each representing a specific viewpoint to monitor the fulfilment of the SO. Two workshops were held to discuss the AC with the LL owners and mentors, one in July and another one in September 2021.

In addition, the WP6 team organised a training session to convey the guidelines to the other WPs which are contributing metrics for the framework, WP2 – Water-smart technologies and concepts, WP4 - Circular economy value chains - and WP5 – Society, Governance, Policy, in July 2021. Here the LNEC team explained the criteria for selecting metrics (indicators, indices and/or levels) within B-WaterSmart, taking into account the recent experience of other projects and monitoring & assessment frameworks.

The present deliverable constitutes a first attempt to identify socioeconomic metrics for use of B-WaterSmart LLs, at the later stage and beyond the term of the project in 2024. It consists of a preliminary list of indicators, which considers, at the stage of submission, the preliminary list of AC agreed with the LL representatives at the workshop held by WP6 on the 29th September (see Annex 2).

Figure 1 - Relation between strategic objectives, assessment criteria and metrics (from LNEC training materials)

The contribution of WP5 (Society, Governance, Policy) is complementary to the inputs of WP2 and WP4, which are submitting their corresponding deliverables with metrics simultaneously (D2.1 and D4.2). The combination of the three contributions will cover the 5 dimensions of the assessment framework: technical, environmental, economic, social and governance. For this reason, the WP5 chose to focus on the SO directly related to the social and governance dimensions: A. Ensuring water for all relevant uses; B - Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society; C. Boosting value creation around water; E. Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation.

The WP5 team dedicated the September 2021 monthly meeting (9th) to defining a strategy and work plan for identifying the metrics and organising the production of D5.2. From them, the team split into two working groups, each one focused specifically on metrics for social (SOC) and governance (GOV) aspects. The selection and discussion of metrics herein included was based on a review of literature, also taking into account the experience of other water focused projects that involved assessing the performance of cities and regions (e.g. City Blueprint performance Framework and RESCCUE). In addition, we organised a discussion with the Project Advisor for WP5, Maria Salvetti, consultant for OECD and the Florence School of Regulation with a long expertise in water governance (6th October).

This document should be considered, for all purposes, as part of an ongoing discussion at an early stage of the B-WaterSmart assessment framework, and therefore a preliminary input from WP5 to WP6. The LLs will join the discussion on which metrics to include in the framework from December 2021, until the submission of the first prototype (V0) in March 2022. According to the work plan set up in D6.1, the final, consistent and agreed list of metrics will be available by M30 and achieved through

the three versions of the framework made available for the LLs' feedbacks (V0 at M19 (preliminary list), V1 at M24 (almost final list) and V2 at M30 (final list, only minor revision allowed to facilitate the work of Task 3.9).

This report follows the guidelines provided by D6.1 to the WP teams, for the development of the water-smartness assessment framework, which aims to identify metrics that:

- a. allow for measurement through reliable sources over the long term;
- b. allow for comparison between cases and for assessing improvements over time;
- c. do not overlap with metrics defined for other dimensions and SO, ensuring a comprehensive and clear assessment (yet the articulation between metrics will be further refined when the combined results of the three deliverables are discussed from December 2021)
- d. while keeping the framework as simple and accessible as possible, cover a wide range of socioeconomic issues, ensuring that proposed metrics are in line with the most recent developments in society, policy and research.

Furthermore, D5.2 considers the general guidance provided by D6.1 that approximately 75% of the metrics should be applicable to all LL, against 25% that can focus on specificities of each city or region involved in the project. As stated, "the framework needs to provide a minimum set of metrics that is able to compare (i) the current state in relations to the LL's own objectives, (ii) developments over time and (iii) between cases".

The definition of the metrics to be included in the B-WaterSmart framework shall comply with the requirements listed below, as stated on the WP6 deliverable – "What is Water-smartness and how to assess it".

Individually, each metric shall:

- *be relevant for the strategic objectives of the LL;*
- *fit in the predefined assessment criteria;*
- *be clearly defined, with a concise meaning;*
- *be reasonably achievable (which mainly depends on the related variables);*
- *be auditable;*
- *be as universal as possible and provide a measure which is independent from the particular conditions of the LL;*
- *be simple and easy to understand;*
- *be quantifiable so as to provide an objective measurement of the service, avoiding any personal or subjective appraisal (best use of already collected data should be made);*
- *include information on the data quality of the variables.*

(from [D6.1.. April 2021](#))

To facilitate the discussion and selection of the metrics, the WP5 team also proposed a list of additional categories, which are included in the Excel file provided in Annex 2 (adapted from the file provided by WP6).

Table 1 - List of additional categories proposed by WP5

Scale	Type	Data source	Periodicity	Target	Method (if primary data)	Most relevant for
City	Qualitative	Official statistics	Daily	Citizens	Interviews	All LLs
Municipal	Quantitative	Official reports	Weekly	Consumers	Survey	Alicante
Regional	Scoring	Academic studies	Monthly	BWS stakeholders	Document analysis	Bodø
National		External institutions	Yearly	BWS partners	Other	East Frisia
European		CoP meetings	10 years		N/A	Flanders
International		Consortium partners	Other			Lisbon
River basin						Venice

Considering the stage of development of the assessment framework, D5.2 focuses mostly on the cross-cutting metrics, however we seek to identify those that are especially relevant for specific LL in the project.

The proposed metrics encompass four indicator types:

- 1) Indicators informed by official databases, mostly quantitative;
- 2) Indicators adopted from the Governance Capacity Framework (GCF) - qualitative with results analysed through a 5 level scoring - interviews & policy documents (Koop et al., 2017);
- 3) New indicators that require data collection, but can be adjusted to the GCF methodology and scoring (with the development of specific contents for each new indicator)
- 4) Other methods of data collection that might involve a different public as well (e.g. through local surveys such as the one carried out in Lisbon for assessing public risk perceptions on wastewater reuse)

During the stage of validation of the metrics proposed, there will be a need to discuss with the LL the strategy for data collection and the feasibility of keeping each metric over the longer term. Other projects have kept their assessment frameworks flexible, so that users could select the components most pertinent to them at some point in time. It is the case of Project RESCCUE - RESilience to cope

with Climate Change in Urban arEas (2016-2020, <https://toolkit.resccue.eu/>). This project involved the creation of a Resilience Assessment Framework for the cities of Barcelona, Bristol and Lisbon (Cardoso et al., 2020) following a multi sectoral approach. The assessment considers different types of metrics that can be selected by the cities, allowing for a combination between general and local-specific metrics, as well as for the selection of those which measurement is most feasible for each city: essential, complementary and comprehensive.

It covers four dimensions: the organisational dimension integrates top-down governance relations and urban population involvement, at the city level. The spatial dimension, also at the city level, refers to urban space and environment. The resilience of strategic services is assessed through the functional dimension, while the physical dimension focuses on the resilience of their infrastructure. These last two dimensions also allow to integrate the contribution of each service to the resilience of the city as whole.

A note about terminology: while we have sought to adequate the WP5 inputs to the Excel template provided by WP6, we acknowledge that there is some variation in terminology between the STEM sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities. There is some variation regarding the relation between such terms as 'metrics' and 'indicators', the latter being often at a higher level than the former in the social sciences (e.g., in surveys). In any case, in an interdisciplinary project such as B-WaterSmart, this is not an issue that interferes with the completion of the metrics list at this point. It is instead a matter for possible debate during the validation stage of the framework, and which should be considered when revising the preliminary list provided on Annex 2.

2.1. Governance Capacity Framework

The Governance Capacity Framework (GCF) has been employed by KWR, one of the partners of B-WaterSmart, in multiple projects, such as the City Blueprint Approach (Koop et al., 2017) and has been adopted by B-WaterSmart (D6.1) as a starting point to develop a methodology to assess water-smartness in what regards key policy and governance issues.

The GCF is a diagnosis tool that consists of three complementary frameworks. The GCF is the one used where cities can improve their water governance. It intends to place the role of urban governance into the context of the challenges that cities across the globe are facing in relation to water, waste and climate change (Koop et al., 2017). It assumes that meeting these challenges requires governance effectiveness, because it entails managing long-term, complex, uncertain, and imperfectly known risks that can have large impacts. Even integrated approaches and a set of other assessment frameworks were unable to fully respond to this level of complexity once they tended to focus more on technical solutions and lesser attention to governance processes. On the other hand, the immense diversity of socioeconomic, cultural and political factors and conditions that impede or enhance the ability to respond proactively to future changes, the GCF came up as a coherent framework that allows assessing different contexts consistently, providing empirical-based understanding to underlie urban water governance processes for transferable lessons that may enhance overall governance effectiveness.

For this reason, and also because this methodology has been extensively applied worldwide, GCF was selected as a prompt assessment framework for the B-WaterSmart SO “Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation”.

Governance is the context that allows policy to be successful. Different policies, apart from being contextually based, require adequate governance models. In the case of urban water governance, policies driven by market, hierarchical regulation or collaborative integrated water planning, for instance, are implemented under normative and regulatory frameworks where governance systems operate. The result of a governance process is to enable actors and citizens to collaborate and address shared problems towards adaptive and co-defined solutions. As defined by Koop et al. (2017), water governance capacity is “the key set of governance conditions that should be developed to enable change that will be effective in finding dynamic solutions for governance challenges of water, waste, and climate change in cities”.

According to these principles, the GCF was thus considered as a baseline to define and select the proper metrics to assess water governance in the 6 LL.

The first step was the constitution of a team of four researchers with experience on governance assessment. Each of them took the same paper as a reference for the GCF methodology (Koop et al., 2017) and a starting point for a review of recent literature that was considered as useful to better respond to the B-WaterSmart goals, especially in what concerns innovation and participatory dimensions. This revision allowed us to identify the gaps in terms of new concepts that have been emerging since 2017, both in policy (e.g. Circular Economy, Water-smartness) and in the literature (Hydrocitizenship). The new concepts thus identified have been shared and discussed within the team in charge of D5.2 and were accepted as complementary contributions to the main GCF methodology.

The GCF is a governance capacity assessment method consisting of three dimensions, nine key conditions and 27 indicators. We present the structure of the framework here, in order to make clear which of the proposed indicators on Annex 2 are derived, or adapted from this assessment framework (table 2).

Table 2 - Governance Capacity Framework

Dimensions	Condition	Indicators
Knowing	1 Awareness	1.1 Community knowledge 1.2 Local sense of urgency 1.3 Behavioral internalization
	2 Useful knowledge	2.1 Information availability 2.2 Information transparency 2.3 Knowledge cohesion
	3 Continuous learning	3.1 Smart monitoring 3.2 Evaluation 3.3 Cross-stakeholder learning
Wanting	4 Stakeholder engagement process	4.1 Stakeholder inclusiveness 4.2 Protection of core values 4.3 Progress and variety of options
	5 Management ambition	5.1 Ambitious and realistic management 5.2 Discourse embedding 5.3 Management cohesion
	6 Agents of change	6.1 Entrepreneurial agents 6.2 Collaborative agents 6.3 Visionary agents
Enabling	7 Multi-level network potential	7.1 Room to manoeuvre 7.2 Clear division of responsibilities 7.3 Authority
	8 Financial viability	8.1 Affordability 8.2 Consumer willingness-to-pay 8.3 Financial continuation
	9 Implementing capacity	9.1 Policy instruments 9.2 Statutory compliance 9.3 Preparedness

(Koop et al., 2017)

The GCF is applied on five water-related governance challenges: Water scarcity; Flood risk; Wastewater treatment; Solid waste treatment; Urban heat islands.

The advantage of putting all these governance challenges together is to avoid typically fragmented scopes, viewpoints and responsibilities, while offering an assessment framework that allows to deal to complexity, uncertainty and disagreement, In fact, it is an iterative process that requires governance capacity to find dynamic long-term solutions that are supported with flexible intermittent targets to anticipate on emerging barriers and changing situations. However, the method to implement GCF is far of being simple and easy doing once it is based in a triangular method that includes:

1. An analysis of policy documents and reports provide preliminary scores of the twenty-seven indicators for each of the five governance challenges
2. At least fifteen interviewees, three for each of the five governance challenges, need to be selected. The most relevant stakeholders are identified, their interdependencies are plotted and key persons from different levels of decision-making are selected. There are twenty-seven predefined questions that the research needs to answer, one for each indicator and specifically asked with regards to the five governance challenges. The questions are open, non-technical,

with follow-up questions to either target specific elements or for further clarification.

3. After the interviews the participants receive the predefined questions with the preliminary indicator scores and are asked to provide constructive feedback and additional information that can be included in the final scoring.

The 27 indicators all have a specific predefined question that the researcher needs to answer for each of the five governance challenges, resorting to documents, reports and in-depth interviews. The answers provide the basis for the indicator score based on a Likert-type method which is specific for each indicator. Here we provide these predefined questions and Likert-type scoring method for each of the twenty-seven indicators.

Despite the usability of this method to assess the SO E of B-WaterSmart - Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation, a critical revision has been made in order to assure both the adequacy of the project specificities and an update of literature for including some concepts and approaches that emerged after the original GCF has been established.

3. Strategic objectives, Assessment Criteria and metrics

This section serves as a supporting guide to Annex 2 – the preliminary list of metrics proposed by WP5. It is organised per assessment criterion, following the letter codes used in the Excel files produced at WP6 workshops with the LL. Sections A to E are organised per SO, which are then divided into sub-sections for each assessment criterion, following the same order of the Annex 2 table. Metrics are shown as bullet points in bold, with the corresponding numbering and indicators.

A. SO “Ensuring water for all relevant uses”

Using data from official databases is particularly challenging when assessing social issues, particularly topics such as awareness and public opinion. For that reason, we have reviewed the key European surveys of public opinion to verify to what extent they could contribute indicators and data for the B-WaterSmart assessment framework. Sources such as the Eurobarometer and the European Social Survey have not contemplated surveys specifically dedicated to water services, or the citizens perceptions about water quality, for instance. In this context, water-related problems are considered to be an ‘older’ environmental issue, along with air pollution. More recently water issues are addressed as part of the overarching subjects of CE (which until very recently was mostly associated with waste management) and climate change. The latter has been the subject of national surveys in the EU (European Social Survey, Eurobarometer), which only indirectly assess issues related to water availability or quality (e.g., droughts). The most recent Eurobarometer survey on climate change, released in July 2021, inquired EU citizens about their main concerns, with climate change scoring above of most topics. Second in most cases, and top concern for some countries, was “poverty, hunger and lack of drinking water,” meaning that water scarcity (or any other concerns related to water, for that matter) was only considered in tandem with other broad concerns, and even so the question referred to the world as a whole, not to Europe or the respondent’s country.

The European Social Survey has applied thematic questionnaires, also on climate change for instance – there are data at national level on ‘public awareness of climate change’ – yet they are not regular and also there are no questions specifically focused on water issues. In sum, surveys regularly carried out at European and national scales prove a very limited source for evaluating ‘water-smart’ societies. In what regards to collecting data on public awareness and perceptions of water-related problems, especially at the scale of the B-WaterSmart LLs - city, municipal and regional scale – there will be a need to resort to alternative sources, such as surveys carried out at regional and local level. In these cases, it is more likely that there will be a need for primary data collection, e.g., through local-based surveys such as that carried out in Lisbon on water reuse (Lisboa E-Nova, 2020).

With the creation of the 17 **Sustainable Development Goals** (SDG) by the United Nations in 2015, a set of targets and indicators was also defined to assess them. The one most directly related to smart water management is SDG 6 - Ensure access to water and sanitation for all, which is then translated into specific targets covering complementing aspects of water accessibility, security and quality:

Target 6.1: Safe and affordable drinking water (by 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all) – indicator 6.1.1 - Safe drinking water (proportion of population using safely managed drinking water services)

Target 6.2: End open defecation and provide access to sanitation and hygiene

UN definition: By 2030, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations. Indicator **6.2.1: Safe sanitation and hygiene** (Proportion of population using (a) safely managed sanitation services and (b) a hand-washing facility with soap and water).

Target 6.3: Improve water quality, wastewater treatment and safe reuse

UN definition: By 2030, improve water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater and substantially increasing recycling and safe reuse globally. SDG INDICATOR 6.3.1 - Safe sanitation and hygiene (proportion of wastewater safely treated); 6.3.2 - Ambient water quality (proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality). Goal: By 2030 improve water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials.

Being a global assessment framework for sustainable development, many of these metrics are most relevant to developing countries, associated with the goals of improving access to quality water. In the case of Western Europe, accessing the levels of quality, accessibility and affordability of water services through these indicators typically results in levels above 90%, as the service levels are already high. A finer analysis will therefore require the identification of additional indicators that go beyond access to basic services.

That was the case in several assessment frameworks for the SDG that have since been co-designed with stakeholders. SDG Local is the example of a framework created in Portugal in direct articulation with local municipalities. It aims not only at adapting SDG monitoring to the European context, but also considers the local specificities of the country.

Regarding SDG 6, the monitoring platform included one indicator per goal: goal 6.1 - proportion of accommodation served by water supply (%); Safe water (percentage of controlled and good quality water for human consumption) (%); 6.2. - Proportion of dwellings served by wastewater drainage (%); and for goal 6.3: proportion of area of surface water bodies with "good and superior" global status (%).

In the case of B-WaterSmart, the SO "ensuring water for all relevant uses" covers issues of water safety and security (A1), accessibility and equity (A2) and financial viability, including affordability of water resources and services (A3).

Characterisation of vulnerable social groups

In order to address issues of justice and equity, first of all there is a need to characterise pertinent vulnerable social groups in each LL, as well as deprived geographical areas or neighbourhoods, in order to cross this information with the data on water access and affordability. The availability of drinking water in public spaces is one of the core principles of the new EU Drinking Water Directive (2020), following initiatives from civil society organisations. This is therefore a good example of a bottom-up process of participation that led to raise the ambition of water public policy, and has now to be considered in the development of monitoring and evaluation systems as well.

As we have previously highlighted in D5.1 (Manual for Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement), the OECD emphasizes the need to involve multiple spheres of stakeholders, including what they call "unrepresented actors" - indigenous communities, the poor, urban slum dwellers, subsistence farmers,

women, the youth, as well as non-water civil society organisations working on governance issues and even nature.

In relation to the target groups, it is both important to evaluate the risk perceptions; willingness to pay of the public/citizens and of the stakeholders who might adopt the B-WaterSmart solutions, such as industries or agriculture organisations. Not only does the engagement process have to be as much inclusive as possible, also the assessment framework should cover the concerns of the traditionally least represented sectors of society. In the European context, this includes assessing water availability and affordability within migrant communities, for instance.

A.1 Safe and secure fit-for-purpose water provision

In our proposed metrics list for B-WaterSmart, the assessment criterion A1 will also cover social concerns pertinent to climate adaptation, namely ensuring water security for all purposes and users (thus including indicators related to water consumption trends – A.1.1. – water quality – A1.2. - and water storage – A.1.5), as well as public safety (A.1.4. - measures for managing the impact of climate extremes, such as flood management). Moreover, we reflect concerns with increasing temperatures in cities and the need to reinforce accessibility of both drinking water and water bodies (for leisure, cooling in heatwaves, etc.) in public spaces and green areas.

Another aspect to consider here is the several target groups of relevance for the assessment framework, from a societal perspective. They include the B-WaterSmart stakeholders, such as representatives of the industry and agriculture sectors, but also citizens and domestic consumers. Therefore, it is important to gain a sense of the public perceptions towards water management at the LL scale, and more specifically towards water-smart solutions such as wastewater reuse (including costs and health risks). This has generally required primary data collection, as was the case in the survey carried out in Lisbon in 2020 (Lisboa E-Nova, 2020). We have therefore included in AC A1 metrics related to **risk perceptions** (water safety - A.1.3), in which cases it will be important to gather information at the LL scale, following the examples of such locally-based surveys.

A2 Accessibility and equity

Concerns with equitable water access have been typically associated with developing countries and have been less explored in the European context over the last few decades. However, more recently there has been an increasing attention from civil society and research to equity, social inclusion and fairness issues in European countries, along with a stronger presence of the social sciences in sustainability research and policy. This has led to the growing inclusion of the equity concerns in assessment frameworks as well, especially as there has been a growing concern with the impacts of climate change in rising inequalities. It becomes obvious that assessing equity in the context of water management has to go much beyond just measuring physical accessibility to water services. It has to account for multiple factors of vulnerability within society. From the perspective of climate adaptation, public accessibility of water in public and green areas is critical, both drinking water, such as in fountains (A.2.1.) and water bodies (A.2.3.). This has been a key concern on the revised Drinking Water Directive, with a focus on vulnerable and marginalised social groups (European Commission, 2020).

Issues of social justice are generally challenging to assess, especially so through quantitative indicators. The recent project BINGO, for instance, has approached these aspects through a survey that was carried out to assess how social justice has been considered in adaptation measures. This

was done by mapping out distributions of burdens and benefits related to the selected adaptation measures at each project site. It seeks to map the existent vulnerabilities in each site, as well as the possible impacts of adaptation strategies in either reinforcing or alleviating them. Moreover, the questionnaire applied equality principles from social theories of justice (e.g. egalitarian) to analyse the design and implementation of adaptation strategies.

Another aspect important to consider for B-WaterSmart is that the assessment framework should take into account the links between water and energy use, as well as waste/wastewater management, along the nexus water-energy-waste-resources. This implies, from the social viewpoint, that **affordability** and access (A.2.2.) should be analysed considering multiple household expenses. Especially at a time when costs of energy are rising sharply in Europe. While this is certainly challenging, the socioeconomic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemics should be considered for any assessment framework that will be in use over the next decade.

Emerging social research in Europe is starting to address the nexus water-energy from the perspective of the vulnerable households. For instance, Yoon and Saurí (2019) have sought to explore water poverty and energy poverty together in Catalonia, Spain, through a holistic understanding of human and nature relationship at the household level. This is a very recent research strand that will be followed by WP5 throughout the duration of B-WaterSmart.

A3 Financial viability

Under AC financial viability the WP5 team chose to include metrics related to water use tariffs. These include the number of **complaints** (A.3.1) - to the water utility and the regulation agency - regarding problems with the applied tariffs and water consumption charges. Both targets of domestic consumers/households and stakeholders are relevant in this context, as financial viability will be a condition for e.g. industry users to consider applying water-smart solutions and joining circular business models.

In parallel with risk perceptions from A1, it is also crucial to assess the **perception of costs** (A.3.2), namely the costs of treatment in order to guarantee safe and secure water provision fit for purpose. Once again, it would be important to assess both the perceptions of the public and the B-WaterSmart stakeholders, as costs for different solutions might operate as a driver or a barrier for their adoption at a broader scale (especially for industry and agriculture stakeholders). A specific indicator that has raised growing interest in the water management sector is the **willingness to pay** (A.3.2) for specific levels of service, which may apply to water supply and to wastewater management and treatment (Willis and Sheldon, 2021). This type of indicator will in principle need to be assessed through surveys, which might be applied to a representative sample of the households, or to the B-WaterSmart stakeholders represented at the Communities of Practice (CoP).

Finally, the **financial continuation** metric (A.3.3) refers to the existence of financial arrangements that can support the implementation of sound and robust long-term policies. It derives from the Governance Capacity Framework methodology (described in section 2.1) and is rated according to an indicator-specific Likert scale that ranges from ++ (very promising) to -- (very limitative).

B. SO “Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society”

B.2 Enhanced ecosystem services to society

Ecosystem services (ESS) are the benefits to human society that are directly attributable to the ecological functioning of ecosystems. This AC replaces the original "liveable cities" to avoid the strong focus on urban areas. The metrics identified to assess the criteria should cover services enhanced in urban, and not urban areas, so to cover all LLs.

There are multiple ways connecting ecosystems and urban or rural areas. The water cycle is directly linked to freshwater or marine ecosystems. There are also a number of connections between water systems and other ecosystems, like terrestrial ecosystems. Anthropogenic activities have a direct impact on these systems but also gain from them. The theory of ESS offers a broad range of possible indicators to assess the relation between ecosystems and society.

Commonly, there is a cascade linking the environment with the social and economic system (Potschin und Haines-Young, 2016). Meaning e.g. a biophysical structure or process (e.g. woodland) has a function (e.g. slow passage of water, evapotranspiration, absorbing CO₂ etc.). Now these can be called intermediate ESS. But these intermediate ESS ultimately lead to the delivery of so-called final services. These final services offer the basis for human well-being. So in the example outlined above, the wood may deliver these final services (EEA, 2018):

- a) Sequestration/storage of CO₂ (2.1.1.1)
- b) Filtration of groundwater (2.1.1.1)
- c) Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation; including flood control, and coastal protection (2.2.1.3)
- d) Wood/timber for direct use or processing; excluding genetic materials (1.1.1.2)
- e) Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment; e.g. recreational activities in the forest (3.1.1.1)

These examples are selected from the Common Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES). CICES is made public by the European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2018). CICES is a prominent and international classification used in academia and gaining growing attention for water management as well. Final services have in common that they are beneficial and of value to society. This means, along the cascade of ecosystems, they are the final link between the environment and the socioeconomic system. The theory of ESS envisions to quantify the benefits and monetize the value of final services. In the example above the storage of CO₂ may be assessed by damage costs avoided from reduced global emissions, the filtration costs avoided in the water treatment plant using good quality groundwater, the damage costs avoided by flood protection for society, market value of wood for direct use or processing and the willingness to pay by local inhabitants and regional tourists enjoying a healthy forest for recreational activities (e.g. hiking or biking in the forest).

Moreover, the examples above show the basic categories of ESS:

- a) Regulating ESS: e.g. Filtration of contaminants/pollution and regulation of natural cycles (B.2.1)
- b) Provisioning ESS: e.g. Provision of basic resources which benefit the local population directly (B.2.2)

- c) Cultural ESS: e.g. Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions (B.2.3)

The ESS theory is a valuable concept to analyse the interconnections between society, environment and water management. Its fundamental theory and practical applications, including a comprehensive list of indicators (CICES), may be a relevant source for the B-WaterSmart assessment framework. It is also a tool to analyse trade-offs between different actions and usages across the water-energy-food nexus. For instance, wood used as building material or energy (wood fuel) cannot serve as filter beneficial for ground water, flood protection or carbon sink. The same conflict arise by a change in land use: e.g. agricultural land gain by deforestation. A growing number of publications, such as Anzaldúa *et al.* (2018) or Gerner *et al.* (2018) from the DESSIN project (<https://dessin-project.eu/>) show how to systematically analyse the relations between society and ecosystems in relation to water management. For B-WaterSmart especially the three categories of ESS may serve as “guiding, broad indicators” (regulating, provisioning and cultural ESS). The selection for specific LLs should be based on the full CICES list and is site specific.

C. SO “Boosting value creation around water”

C.1. Circular Policy Making

Beyond the existence of policy instruments – **plans and strategies** (C.1.2) - dedicated to implementing a CE, it is also crucial to identify policy and process indicators that allow to capture the implementation of specific CE policy measures and initiatives, in particular for the water sector. The most commonly used policy indicator by Governments is the **Green Public Procurement (GPP)** (C1.1), used as a proxy for market creation for CE products and services (PACE, 2021). GPP numbers isolated do not say much about the actual circularity of what is being procured, it is also important to understand the CE criteria that are being applied. In this particular context, there is a GPP criteria for wastewater infrastructure projects (European Commission, 2013). The use of GPP criteria is an opportunity for waste water managing authorities to build and operate wastewater infrastructures reducing environmental impact.

Related to circular policy making, Potting and Hanemaaije (2018) proposed indicators to measure new and changed regulations that permit CE (e.g. number of legal and regulatory barriers to the CE removed and description of new standards and regulations changing ‘linear’ regulations).

C.5 Level of ambition

In order to measure innovatively the level of ambition of policies for promoting the circular economy, we have selected two indicators for assessing **innovative policy design** (C5.1 and C5.2). One indicator, included in the EU’s set of 10 CE monitoring indicators, is the number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials as a proxy for innovation (European Commission, 2018). This indicator has its own limitations as it fails to fully cover the features of circularity (e.g., innovation in business models) (PACE, 2021), but can be used in conjunction with the other metrics proposed to assess the level of water-smart innovation in a LL. Complementing this indicator, the WP5 team proposes to consider the incorporation of recovered materials and nutrients in the value chains across the nexus water-energy-waste (C5.2).

E. SO “Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation”

E.1 Awareness

In the GCF, awareness is understood as a prerequisite to enable effective change, both cognitively and emotionally felt by individuals, organisations, and society (cf. Ballard, 2008) and forming the base for learning and action (cf. Adger et al., 2009). Within this framework it is assessed by the indicators community knowledge, local sense of urgency and behavioral internalisation (Koop et al., 2017). The aspects concerning knowledge and co-learning are now integrated into E3 – Stakeholder engagement processes and E5 - Information and knowledge sharing. In its current version, additional metric proposed by the WP5 team are integrated in E.1. – Awareness..

We have considered, in Annex 2, an additional metric of contextualisation for assessment criterion Awareness (E.1) – **public attitudes towards climate change** (E1.1), which can be sourced from European and national surveys such as the European Social Survey and the Eurobarometer.

A key source of data on public perceptions, which can support this sort of metrics, is the European Social Survey. Since its inception in 2001, the European Social Survey has been a cross-national academically driven survey that has been performed across Europe. Face-to-face interviews with newly selected cross-sectional samples are performed every two years. The study examines the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours patterns of people over thirty countries.

The module on public attitudes toward climate change, energy security, and energy preferences was used in 2016 and covers four broad areas, namely (1) beliefs about climate change, (2) concerns about climate change and energy security, (3) personal norms, efficacy, and trust, and (4) energy preferences in several European countries (e.g., Norway, Netherlands, Portugal Spain, Germany, Italy, among others). This module was designed to achieve specific main objectives, namely: 1) to create a comprehensive, theoretically cross-wide dataset of public attitudes to climate change, energy security and energy preferences; 2) to develop an understanding of how socio-political, economic and environmental factors at the national level shape public attitudes to energy and climate change across Europe; 3) examine the role of socio-political values and other individual-level factors in Europeans' attitudes toward energy and climate change; and 4) examine the relative importance of both individual-motivational factors and national circumstances in the public's preferences for different sources of energy supply sources and demand reduction.

Although the focus of the survey was not directly related to water, the indicators used can be easily adapted to this area. From the list of indicators that could measure the level of awareness of citizens, we highlight those that measure the level of concern of citizens regarding climate change and the level of their knowledge about this issue, their personal responsibility for reducing the consequences of climate change and the level of concern about climate change. These indicators were measured by using 4- and 5-point Likert scales (e.g., climate change awareness: 1=definitely changing; 2=probably changing; 3=probably not changing; 4=definitely not changing; climate change worries: 1= not at all worried; 2=not very worried; 3=somewhat worried; 4=very worried; 5=extremely worried).

There are different levels of awareness that should be distinguished:

Public education and awareness – which can be assessed through carrying out surveys to representative samples of the local population or to a representative sample of the consumers/households served by a given water utility;

Awareness of the stakeholders (e.g. industries) in relation to water-smart solutions and strategies (E1.3) – which can be assessed through quantitative methods such as surveys, but also through interviews and focus groups (which can be organised within the CoP, e.g. in between plenary meetings);

Awareness of **decision and policy makers** (E1.3) - in relation to the previous point, it is crucial to assess and better understand awareness among decision and policy-makers themselves. These are a fundamental group of stakeholders within B-WaterSmart, as policies and regulations will constitute determinant drivers (or barriers) for the implementation of water-smart solutions during the project and beyond.

Once the assessment framework is to be applied by B-WaterSmart LL, they should select which of these three levels of awareness would better fit in their contexts.

Considering that it is very difficult to meaningfully assess public education and awareness through a representative sample, the WP5 team considered that it would be relevant to propose additional metrics that would allow for a more integrated performance.

That is where the emerging concept of **hydrocitizenship** (E1.2) comes up - a concept proposed by the research project “Towards Hydrocitizenship”, which could also be integrated into the B-WaterSmart framework as a complementing metric of awareness. Whatmore et al. (2019) conducted this interdisciplinary study, in which they investigate “the ways in which citizens and communities live with each other and their environment in relation to water in a range of UK neighbourhoods” (<http://www.hydrocitizenship.com>). In this approach, the prefix “hydro” signs the idea that the material, cultural, and political-economic specificities of water make it a particularly important realm through which to study emerging understandings and practices of citizenship, democratic life, and efforts to manage human/environment relations.’ It implies an awareness of and a responsibility for water as a vital social and environmental resource at both the individual and community level. This concept is closely related to E3 since it allows to measure the precondition of citizenship as a basis for engagement and action embedding.

Depending on the context of each LL, it may include concerns over flooding, sea level rise, climate change, drought and supply security, water quality, biodiversity and landscape quality, access for recreation, water and energy, effective urban drainage, and waste management. Community, although a now much challenged and questioned term, remains a key way of thinking about how society can function effectively in social, cultural and economic terms.

Therefore, we may ask, what does it do to the ways in which we imagine communities, and to the ways in which they imagine themselves, if local water-related environmental issues (both assets and conflicts) are brought more fully into local public consciousness? Can addressing environmental issues through local groups help develop relations within communities and between communities? Can narratives of past and current relationships between people, and people and water, help generate new

narratives – new relationships, new behaviours? Can it impact positively on building a water-smart society and raising the public acceptance of water-smart solutions?

Furthermore, the criteria reflects **discourse embedding** (E1.4). Discourse embedding answers the question: to what extent is sustainable policy interwoven in historical, cultural, normative and political context? This metric is derived from the GCF and will be assessed through the analysis of policy documents.

In Annex 1 we propose specific questions to assess the metrics proposed in this section, following the methodology of the GCF.

E.2 Multi-level network potential

Multi-level network potential is one of the conditions included in the GCF and should include metrics such as Room to manoeuvre, Clear division of responsibilities, Authority and Long-term commitment, as discussed in the workshops with the LL.

E.2. regards the assessment of organisation's ability to cooperate across multiple levels, horizontally and vertically. Metrics herein proposed pertaining to interaction for common objectives and sharing responsibilities across governance levels (E2.1: **multi-level network**), but also horizontally between different sectors (E2.2: **cross-sectorial capacity**), such as wastewater treatment and industry. This assessment criterion is particularly relevant in articulation with C. (Circular Economy) to assess the capacity of stakeholders to engage in new circular business models and create synergies, as well as supports the development of new governance models.

Transboundary cooperation (E2.3) is an additional metric proposed, taking into account that in some LLs (ex. Flanders) there are environmental pressures that require cooperation across administrative and national borders, especially at the river basin level.

In Annex 1 we propose specific questions to assess the metrics proposed in this section, following the methodology of the GCF.

E.3 Stakeholder Engagement processes and Learning

The WP5 team proposes to focus this assessment criterion not only on stakeholder engagement processes but also on learning, and therefore proposes to add learning to the title.

The assessment criteria "stakeholder engagement" adopted in the GCF seems appropriate for the B-WaterSmart assessment framework. The stakeholder engagement process consists of stakeholder inclusiveness, protection of core values and progress, as well as variety of options.

Stakeholder inclusiveness refers to the extent to which the representatives are able to speak and decide on behalf of all relevant stakeholders in clear and transparent engagement processes. Protection of core values refers to the importance of ensuring that all stakeholders feel confident that their core values are not harmed, in order to create a safe environment for trust relationships (Koop et al., 2017).

As for learning, “continuous learning is required, in order to adapt to changing situations with many uncertainties, complexities, and unknowns” (Folke et al. 2005, cited in Koop et al., 2017). The learning criteria herein proposed focuses on what is learned (content), thus complementing the GCF approach that focuses on how learning occurs (process).

Concerning what is learned, learning refers to the change in understanding of a subject that takes the form of change in knowledge, skills, capabilities, beliefs, behaviour, practices or relationships. Learning can occur at the level of individuals, groups, organisations and society. Co-learning (E.3.1) refers specifically to group learning via engagement of citizens and stakeholders across sectors on a specific topic.

A functional approach to what is learned distinguishes: relational learning, cognitive learning and strategic learning.

1. **Relational learning** (E.3.2): improved understanding of mind sets of others, enhanced trust and ability to cooperate of individuals, groups and organizations which manifest with, for example, new or consolidated relationships and networks, shared understanding of problems and solutions, knowledge co-production activities (Haug *et al.*, 2011);

2. **Cognitive learning** (E.3.3): The acquisition of new knowledge, or the improved structuring of existing knowledge of individuals, groups and organizations that manifest e.g. as acquired new skills, changed values and beliefs, novel/adapted practices (Haug *et al.*, 2011);

3. **Strategic learning** (E.3.4): The improved capacity and means to develop a long-term, strategic orientation of a group or organization intended as its vision, long-term goals and position in the socioeconomic and political context that manifest e.g. in changed practices in organizing work, human and financial resources, strategic alliances (Kuwada, 1998).

These aspects will be challenging to assess, as for instance holding multiple stakeholder engagement events does not necessary reflect on an effective level of engagement and impact. This issue has been discussed in workshops with the LL, and it has been proposed to combine an assessment of the number of initiatives (from CoP meetings monitoring or stakeholder surveys) with qualitative indicators of impact. In the preliminary list (Annex 2), and drawing insights from recent literature on water governance (Williams *et al.*, 2018), the WP5 team proposes to include metrics on number of participants in public meetings (differentiated per sector), number of years representatives assume their roles (as an indication of trust building), and previous examples of conflict resolution.

E.4 Capacity building

Concerning how learning occurs, in the GCF continuous learning is assessed by smart monitoring, evaluation and cross-stakeholder learning. Smart monitoring is a precondition for learning and may serve as a tool for identifying alarming situations, clarifying underlying processes, and predicting future developments. Regular monitoring and evaluation are imperative for continuous learning and enhance preparedness for uncertain futures (Koop et al., 2017). Here, both indicators were included as part of the assessment criterion E4. In E.4 the first two indicators – smart monitoring (E.4.1) and evaluation (E.4.2) – are directly adopted from the GCF model, and will thus be assessed based on interviews to stakeholders and the scoring of the qualitative results (see Methodology, section 2.1).

In addition, the WP5 team proposed to include ‘**transformative capacity**’ as a complementing metric (E.4.3), in addition to technical, strategic and adaptive capacity. While some of its dimensions may be

covered under other AC, **urban sustainability foresight and community experimentation with disruptive solutions** could be emphasized here. Brodrik and Brown (2018), citing Wolfram (2016), describe the former as 'transdisciplinary knowledge production and agreement on future pathways, normative questions and feasibility issues that inform actionable policies' where key elements & possible metrics could be i) sharing a compelling sustainability vision for radical changes by many and providing orientation to different actors, ii) clarification of options by alternative scenarios and future pathways for action and critical thresholds. The latter is described as 'visionary and holistic experimentation with path-deviant innovation to develop transformative knowledge and catalyse social learning'. Key elements; i) undertaking diverse practice experimentation by different CoPs guided by a shared vision, ii) experimentation with disruptive practices that seek multidimensional (e.g. technological, cultural) changes for sustainability (these two could probably be reduced to one).

The concept of triple-loop learning that is included in the GCF¹ is broad and could in principle cover the concept of transformative capacity partially, but we would still recommend (or at least bring up the point for reflection) that transformative capacity, with emphasis on foresight and experimentation could be highlighted especially, seeing transformative capacity as something that goes beyond adaptive capacity to encompass more profound processes of social change.

E.5 Information and knowledge sharing

The first three metrics included under this assessment criterion are derived from the GCF and follow the same scoring methodology – information availability (E.5.1), information transparency (E.5.2) and knowledge cohesion (E.5.3).

Preliminary definition based on other studies (Koop et al., 2017): *'The field of information science distinguishes between data, information and knowledge (Zins, 2007). Data in itself is not necessarily informative, as useful knowledge can only be obtained by data interpretation and analysis (Zins, 2007; Rowley 2007; Van Leeuwen, 2007).*

Information availability refers to the extent that knowledge is available, reliable, and based on multiple sources and methods (Koop et al., 2021). A lack of knowledge inhibits informed decision-making (Rowley 2007; Van Rijswick et al., 2014). Many cities authorities recognize the lack of knowledge of how future trends, such as urbanization and climate change, will affect them (Amundsen et al., 2010). Table 3 shows the evaluation criteria used for the 5-point score.

¹ The theory of triple-loop learning is used in the GCF, with three levels: 1) single-loop learning which is incremental learning to refine current management and policy; 2) double-loop learning refers to the critical investigation of assumptions and key relationships, which reframes problems; 3) triple-loop learning questions underlying norms and values and can transform the wider social and institutional structure (Koop et al., 2017)

Table 3 - Evaluation criteria for the 5-point score

++	Comprehensive information enabling long-term integrated policy	A comprehensive and integrated documentation of the issue can be found on local websites and policy papers. It is characterized with adequate information, an integrated description of social, ecological and economic processes regarding the water challenge, as well as goals and policies. Furthermore, progress reports on effective implementation can be found
+	Information enhancing integrated long-term thinking	Strong effort is put in providing integrated information from various fragmented sources. Information gaps are identified and attempted to be bridged. This may be clear from extensive documentation on the long-term process. Also citizen knowledge may be taken into account
0	Information fits demand, limited exploratory research	Information on the water challenge is available. Knowledge on understanding or tackling the water challenge is progressing and is produced in a structural way. Knowledge gaps are hardly identified due to lock-in into existing disciplines and policy. This is apparent from the quantity of factual information, but the causes, risks and impacts of long-term processes are lacking behind
-	Information scarcity and limited quality	Limited information is available which does not grasp the full extent of the water challenge. In some cases not all information is of sufficient quality to generate a comprehensive overview
--	Lack of information	No information on the water challenge can be found. Or the scarce available information is of poor quality

(Koop et al., 2021)

- **Information transparency** refers to the effective communication and sharing or co-creation of knowledge with all interested stakeholders. The information needs to be good quality, credible, understandable, and accessible for non-experts, in order to prevent miscommunication, knowledge gaps, and fragmented policy (Lemos et al., 2012; Füssel, 2007). Recent studies on transparency in the water sector highlighted that availability of information is just a part of the process, it does not ensure, per se, that stakeholders and citizens actually have influence in policy and management processes. There is a need to assess their own perceptions as well (Stefano et al., 2016). Table 4 gives the evaluation criteria used for the 5-point score.

Table 4 - Evaluation criteria for the 5-point score

++	Easy access to cohesive knowledge	Information is easily accessible on open source information platforms. There are multiple ways of accessing and sharing information. Information is often provided by multiple sources and is understandable for non-experts
+	Sharing of partly cohesive knowledge	All interested stakeholders can access information. Action has been taken to make knowledge increasingly understandable. Still, it is a time-consuming search through a maze of organizations, protocols and databases to abstract cohesive knowledge and insights
0	Sharing of very technical knowledge	There are protocols for accessing information; however, it is not readily available. Although information is openly available, it is difficult to access and comprehend because it is very technical. The water challenge is reported on local websites and reports
-	Low sharing of fragmented knowledge	Information is sometimes shared with other stakeholders. However, information is inaccessible for most stakeholders. Furthermore, knowledge is often technical and difficult to understand for non-experts. The water challenge may be addressed on local websites
--	Not transparent and inaccessible knowledge	Information is limitedly available and shared. sharing may be discouraged. The information that is available is difficult to understand. The water challenge is not addressed on local websites

(Koop et al., 2021)

- **Knowledge cohesion** refers to the conformity of knowledge across actors, sectors, and administrative layers. Table 5 gives the AC used for this indicator in the GCF.

Table 5 - Evaluation criteria for the 5-point score

++	Implementation of cohesive knowledge	Stakeholders are engaged in long-term and integrated strategies. Information can be found that is co-created knowledge and will contain multiple sources of information, multiple and mixed methods taking into account the socio-, ecological and economic aspects of the water challenge
+	Substantial cohesive knowledge	Sectors cooperate in a multidisciplinary way, resulting in complete information regarding the water challenge. Besides multiple actors, multiple methods are involved to support information. Too many stakeholders are involved, sometimes in an unbalanced way. Knowledge about effective implementation is often limited
0	Insufficient cohesion between sectors	Data collection within sectors is consistent and is sustained in multiple projects for about two to three election periods. Knowledge on the water challenge, however, is still fragmented. This becomes clear from different foci of the stakeholders as stated in their organisation's strategies and goal setting
-	Low-cohesive knowledge within sectors	Information that is found is sector specific and information is inconsistent within and between sectors
--	Non-cohesive and contradicting knowledge	A lack of data strongly limits the cohesion between sectors. Information that is found can even be contradictory

(Koop et al., 2021)

In addition, WP5 proposed two new metrics, one to be assessed through the same methodology:

Knowledge usage (E.5.4): One indicator to measure knowledge use would be the number of times knowledge was shared or reused in the development of new policies or implementation of water-smart solutions.

Knowledge sharing (E.5.5): Giving regard to the OECD’s Water Governance Principle 5 “Data and Information”², it would be advisable to develop a specific indicator for knowledge sharing, as an important part of knowledge management, in order to measure both the efficiency and effectiveness of the knowledge sharing process. For instance, it would be interesting to analyse the existence and level of implementation of knowledge and experience sharing mechanisms and if stakeholders use the newly acquired knowledge in managerial decisions to adapt and improve policies and programmes.

Table 6 - Scoring for knowledge sharing

++	Implementation of knowledge sharing
+	Substantial knowledge sharing
0	Limited knowledge sharing
-	Insufficient knowledge sharing
--	Lack of knowledge sharing

² Produce, update and share timely, consistent, comparable, and policy-relevant water and water-related data and information, and use it to guide, assess and improve water policy, through defining requirements for cost-effective and sustainable production and methods for sharing high-quality water and water-related data and information (e.g. on the status of water resources, water financing, environmental needs, socio-economic features and institutional mapping) and fostering effective coordination and experience-sharing among organisations and agencies producing water-related data between data producers and users, and across levels of government.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

In its current version, the WP5 preliminary proposal for metrics is a combination of multiple approaches, data sources and methods, as well as different target groups of interest for B-WaterSmart, and especially for evaluating how far a LL has gone in becoming a 'water-smart society'. At this stage, it is possible that the proposals are still generic and present some redundancies. This is a very early stage of development of the metrics (that started when the AC are still under discussion with the LL), which will have to be further refined, and also validated with the LL representatives after December 2021.

We have sought to outline the main options in selecting metrics, as well as the experiences with the use of other assessment frameworks and projects in similar areas, so that the WP teams, and also later the LLs, have a comprehensive view of the trade-offs and advantages involved in selecting specific indicators. For this reason we propose additional categories to be added to the Excel template provided by WP6 for the WP5 inputs regarding the metrics for the social and governance dimensions.

This version of the metrics has considered, for instance, that different target groups are relevant for assessing different aspects of water-smart innovation, such as:

- Stakeholders, namely CoP members such as policy-makers and industry associations/companies
- Consumers (end-users and households)
- Citizens and the public at large

There is also some variation in terms of scale. Some data are only available at the national level (national statistics offices), however they can serve as a reference for data collection at the regional and local level, for instance. The scale of reference for the B-WaterSmart assessment framework will be the LL, but this is not the same across the project, as some LL are municipalities and others are regions. At the current draft version we leave this issue open to be adjusted to the circumstances of each LL accordingly.

It also encompasses multiple data sources and methods. Although the guidance from WP6 is to try and base the assessment as much as possible on secondary data from official databases, evaluation of social and governance issues usually requires a dedicated collection of data. In this case, we have metrics derived from existing methodologies, such as the discussed GCF, but also cases where a different method for data collection might be required. Herein we consider four indicator types:

- 1) Indicators informed by official databases, mostly quantitative;
- 2) Indicators from the GCF - qualitative with results analysed through a 5 level scoring - interviews & documents;
- 3) New indicators that require data collection, but can be adjusted to the GCF methodology and scoring (with the development of specific contents for each new indicator)
- 4) Other methods of data collection that might involve a different public as well (e.g. through local surveys such as the one carried out in Lisbon for assessing public risk perceptions on wastewater reuse)

Although the first indicator type is usually reliable and easier to access on a regular basis, currently they do not cover the whole diversity of issues that are of concern for a water-smart society. There are emerging topics of concern that have not yet been fully addressed in monitoring and evaluation systems in the European context, such as equity issues, or new circumstances such as the pandemic crisis of COVID-19.

Whenever data collection from stakeholders is required, this process can be organised within the CoP, possibly in between meetings and through interviews, focus groups and/or surveys. This still holds beyond the term of B-WaterSmart, assuming that the CoPs will be working as a key mechanism for stakeholder engagement over the long term. It will have to be aligned, in addition, with the ongoing WP5 analysis of drivers and barriers to the implementation of water-smart solutions, including dedicated analysis of social acceptance issues.

Acknowledging that the proposals might appear complex at this point, we seek to provide enough detail to allow for an informed decision and further discussion of the WP5 metrics. It is possible, though, that some of the indicators mentioned can be covered by existing monitoring systems at the local level - municipalities and water utilities in each LL. This can be verified and discussed during the validation stage with the LL representatives.

Another aspect important to consider for B-WaterSmart is that ideally the assessment framework should take into account the links between water and energy use, as well as waste/wastewater management, along the nexus water-energy-waste-resources. This implies, from the social viewpoint, that affordability and access, for instance (AC A), should be analysed considering multiple expenses, especially at a time when costs of energy are rising sharply in Europe. While this is certainly challenging, the socioeconomic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemics should be considered for any assessment framework that will be in use over the next decade.

Finally, during the process of validation there will be a need to analyse how the metrics could operate in practice through the online water-smartness dashboard, and assess technical and practical aspects that might arise when testing the first prototypes.

5. References

- Anzaldúa G., Gerner N. V., Lago M., Abhold K., Hinzmann M., Beyer S., Winking C., Riegels N., Jensen J. K., Termes M., Amorós J., Wencki K., Strehl C., Ugarelli R., Hasenheit M., Nafó I., Hernandez M., Vilanova E., Damman S., Brouwer S., Rouillard J., Schwesig D., Birk S. (2018): Getting into the water with the Ecosystem Services Approach: The DESSIN ESS evaluation framework. *Ecosystem Services*, (30), 318-326.
- Brodnik, C. and R. Brown (2018). Strategies for developing transformative capacity in urban water management sectors: The case of Melbourne, Australia. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 137:147-159.
- Cardoso, M.A., Brito, R.S., Pereira, C., David, L., Almeida, M.C. (2020) RESCCUE: Resilience Assessment Framework - Description and implementation. <https://toolkit.resccue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/D6.4.pdf>
- European Commission (2013). Green public procurement criteria for waste water infrastructure: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3b040254-3bfb-11ea-ba6e-01aa75ed71a1>
- European Commission (2018b). Communication from the Commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions on a monitoring framework for the circular economy: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A29%3AFIN>
- European Commission (2020) "Commission welcomes final agreement on water quality and access to drinking water", https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_2417 (consulted on 29 November 2021)
- European Social Survey (2016). ESS Round 8 Module on Climate Change and Energy – Question Design Final Module in Template. London: ESS ERIC Headquarters c/o City University London.
- Folke, C., Hahn, T., Olsson, P., & Norberg, J. (2005). Adaptive governance of social-ecological systems. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, 441-473.
- Gerner N. V., Nafó I., Winking C., Wencki K., Strehl C., Wortberg T., Niemann A., Anzaldúa G., Lago M., Birk S. (2018): Large-scale river restoration pays off: A case study of ecosystem service valuation for the Emscher restoration generation project. *Ecosystem Services*, 30, 327-338.
- Haines-Young, R. and M.B. Potschin (2018): Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES)
- Haug, C., Huitema, D., and Wenzler, I. (2011). Learning through games? Evaluating the learning effect of a policy exercise on European climate policy. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 78(6): 968–981.
- Jiménez, A.; Saikia, P.; Giné, R.; Avello, P.; Leten, J.; Liss Lymer, B.; Schneider, K.; Ward, R. (2020). Unpacking water governance: A framework for practitioners. *Water* 12.3: 827. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12030827>

- Koop, S.H.A., Koetsier, L., Doornhof, A. et al. (2017). Assessing the Governance Capacity of Cities to Address Challenges of Water, Waste, and Climate Change. *Water Resour Manage* 31, 3427–3443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-017-1677-7>
- Koop, S.H.A. (2021). Indicator of the Water Governance Capacity Framework, KRW.
- Kuwada, K. (1998). Strategic learning: The continuous side of discontinuous strategic change. *Organization Science*, 9(6): 719–736.
- Lisboa E-Nova (2020). Estudo de Atitudes e Comportamentos Face à Reutilização de Água Residual Tratada em Lisboa [Study on Attitudes and Behaviours Towards Wastewater Reuse in Lisbon]. CEMOWAS2/Interreg Sudoe.
- OECD (2018). Implementing the OECD Principles on Water Governance: Indicator Framework and Evolving Practices, OECD Studies on Water; OECD Publishing: Paris, France.
- Pooting and Hanemaaije (2018). Circular economy: what we want to know and can measure. System and baseline assessment for monitoring the progress of the circular economy in the Netherlands: www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2018-circular-economy-what-we-want-to-know-and-can-measure-3217.pdf
- PACE (2021). Circular Indicators for Governments Accelerating action in the circular economy: https://pacecircular.org/sites/default/files/2021-04/CircularIndicatorsForGovernments_FINAL.pdf
- Potschin M., Haines-Young R. (2016): Defining and measuring ecosystem services. In: Potschin, M., Haines-Young, R., Fish, R. and Turner, R.K. (eds) *Routledge Handbook of Ecosystem Services*. Routledge, London and New York, 25-44.
- Stefano, L. D., Empinotti, V., Schmidt, L., Jacobi, P. R., Ferreira, J. G., & Guerra, J. (2016). Measuring Information Transparency in the Water Sector: What Story Do Indicators Tell?. *International Journal of Water Governance*, 1, 1-22.
- Whatmore S, Sarmiento E, Landström C. (2019) Biopolitics, discipline, and hydro- citizenship: Drought management and water governance in England. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*. 44(2):361-375. doi:10.1111/tran.12288
- Williams, D.S.; Máñez Costa, M.; Celliers, L.; Sutherland, C. Informal Settlements and Flooding: Identifying Strengths and Weaknesses in Local Governance for Water Management. *Water* 2018, 10, 871. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10070871>
- Willis, K. & Sheldon, R. (2021) Research on customers' willingness-to-pay for service changes in UK water company price reviews 1994–2019, *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, doi: [10.1080/21606544.2021.1927850](https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2021.1927850)
- Wolfram, M. (2016). Conceptualizing urban transformative capacity: a framework for research and policy. *Cities* 51: 121-130.
- Yoon, H. and Saurí, D. (2019) 'No more thirst, cold, or darkness!' – Social movements, households, and the coproduction of knowledge on water and energy vulnerability in Barcelona, Spain,

Energy Research & Social Science, Volume 58, 101276, ISSN 2214-6296,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101276>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629618309861>)

6. Online references

Eurobarometer (2021). <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/screen/home>. European Union.

European Environment Agency – EEA (2018): CICES V5.1, 18/03/2018. <https://cices.eu/resources/>.

European Social Survey (2021). <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/>. ESS ERIC

ANNEX 1 – GCF methodology applied to additional metrics proposed

Besides adopting the GCF as part of the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework, the WP5 team has proposed in D5.2 some additional metrics. In order to provide a better understanding on how the GCF methodology data collection and scoring methodology can be applied in these cases, we have included examples of the questions to be included in the stakeholder interviews, as well as the corresponding tables with the 5-level criteria for scoring the answers.

E1 - Awareness

E.1.1. Hydrocitizenship

Ability to engage citizens and local communities to establish a water culture to link policy, society, economy and environment in what concerns the acceptance of water smart solutions and the adoption of new behaviours towards a sustainable management of water resources.

Questions:

- Are there any specific initiatives to engage local communities to water smart solutions?
- Is there a community sense of water culture that may express the awareness to save water and to open room for the water smart solutions acceptance?
- What are the main drivers to raise awareness on water smart solutions?
- To what extent do community-based initiatives on water culture may impact positively on healthier communities, resolving conflicts within and between communities, and make progress towards interconnected communities and environmental/water resilience?

Scoring:

++	High level of hydrocitizenship	The local community is fully engaged and committed to adopt all the necessary procedures towards a water-smart society, as well as totally aware and responsible for an efficient water management. This community expresses its culture of water through various participatory initiatives that involve all groups of citizens, assuming water as a central resource for human and environmental well-being.
+	Medium level of hydrocitizenship	Some groups of the local community are engaged and committed to adopt some procedures towards a water-smart society. Only some citizens are aware and responsible for an efficient water management. Punctually this community expresses its culture of water through participatory initiatives that involve some groups of citizens. Water is important but not necessarily understood as the most central resource for human and environmental well-being.

0	Limited level of hydrocitizenship	Only some citizens of the local community are engaged and committed to adopt some procedures towards a water-smart society. Few people are aware and responsible for an efficient water management. Very punctually this community expresses its culture of water through participatory initiatives that involves some groups of citizens. Water is not the central resource for human and environmental well-being.
-	Low level of hydrocitizenship	Due to some unequal access to water utilities, there are some conflicts on water management. The local community is not aware of what a water-smart society might be. There are some initiatives to raise awareness, but low levels of public participation. Water is important for human and environmental well-being, but water management is not responding well to local needs.
--	Inexistent level of hydrocitizenship	There is neither engagement nor commitment to adopt procedures towards a water-smart society. Citizens are not aware of how water management works and what it entails. There is no culture of water. Water is not perceived as a resource that connects to human and environmental well-being.

E.1.2. Stakeholder/Decision-maker education and awareness

Stakeholder and Decision-maker education and awareness is determinant on water policy design and water smart solutions implementation once it influences their perception and preferences for best management practices. They must be determined either by exogenous factors such as demographics, general environmental awareness, politics, socioeconomic context, and endogenous factors like, age, gender, level of education, domain of graduation, socio-cultural provenience and institutional affiliation.

Metrics:

Identification of dominant profile or pattern of stakeholders and decision-makers profiles regarding expectations on opportunities and barriers for implementing the best management practices of water management. It might allow anticipating eventual conflicts of interest or constraints on water-smart solutions acceptance and adoption. It might also support the CoP dynamics in terms of capacity-building and specific training initiatives to solve eventual gaps of knowledge and skills to operate on sustainable water management whilst facilitating the co-learning process. A survey will be conducted and contents will be treated through a statistic analysis (e.g., principal components analysis).

Questions:

- Do you feel enough skilled to take responsibility on the transition to a smarter society?

- Do you feel confident on the approaches to implement water-smart solutions in your Living Lab?
- Do you feel enthusiastic to raise awareness within the community that will adopt new water management solutions?
- Which drivers do you identify to influence the social acceptance of your community to adopt water smart solutions?

Scoring:

++	High level of education and awareness	Most stakeholders and decision-makers are well skilled and willing to make the transition towards a smarter society, especially in what concerns sustainable water management. They are fully committed to influence the policy design and the implementation of collaborative strategies to enlarge the public acceptance of water smart solutions.
+	Medium level of education and awareness	Some stakeholders and decision-makers are well skilled and willing to make the transition towards a smarter society, especially in what concerns sustainable water management. Only some are committed to influence the policy design and the implementation of collaborative strategies to enlarge the public acceptance of water smart solutions.
0	Limited level of education and awareness	Few stakeholders and decision-makers are well skilled and willing to make the transition towards a smarter society, especially in what concerns sustainable water management. There is limited capacity to influence the policy design and the implementation of collaborative strategies to enlarge the public acceptance of water smart solutions.
-	Low level of education and awareness	Stakeholders and decision-makers are not well skilled to make the transition towards a smarter society, especially in what concerns sustainable water management. There is weak capacity to influence the policy design and the implementation of collaborative strategies to enlarge the public acceptance of water smart solutions.
--	Inexistent level of education and awareness	There are conflicts amongst stakeholders and decision-makers due to a lack of capacity to make the transition towards a smarter society happen, especially in what concerns sustainable water management. There is no possibility to influence the policy design and the implementation of collaborative strategies to enlarge the public acceptance of water smart solutions.

References:

Yi Du, Xiaoyan Wang, Lulu Zhang, Karl-Heinz Feger, Jennie Popp, Andrew Sharpley, 2019. Multi-stakeholders' preference for best management practices based on environmental awareness.

Journal of Cleaner Production, Volume 236, 117682, ISSN 0959-6526.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.117682>.

OECD, 2015. Stakeholder Engagement for Inclusive Water Governance. OECD studies on water. OECD Publishing, Paris. http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264231122_en

E.1.3. Discourse embedding

Predefined question: To what extent is sustainable policy interwoven in the historical, cultural, normative and political context?

++	Embedding of sustainable implementations	Local context is used smartly to accelerate policy implementation. Innovations are subdivided into suitable phases which are more acceptable and effectively enables sustainable practices. Effective policy implementation is enabled by a general consensus that long- term integrated policy is needed to address the water challenge
+	Consensus for sustainable actions	There is a consensus that adaptation is required, but substantial effort is necessary as there is little experience in addressing the water challenge in a long-term integrated approach. Furthermore, the decision-making periods are long as trust relations with new unconventional partners need to be built
0	Low sense of urgency embedded in policy	Current policy fits the local context. The water challenge is increasingly identified, framed and interwoven into local discourse, but the disregard of uncertainty prevents a sense of urgency that is necessary to adopt adequate adaptation measures. Decision making often results in very compromised small short-term policy changes
-	Persistent reluctance and poor embedding	Actors feel reluctant to execute current policy as it conflicts with their norms and values. Policy hardly takes the local context and existing discourses into account. And the policy does not correspond with societal demands. This may lead to distrust between actors, inefficient use of resources and ineffective overall implementation
--	Policy mismatch	Cultural, historical and political context is largely ignored, leading to a policy mismatch arduous policy implementation. Actors may not understand the scope, moral or to whom it applies or how to implement it (total confusion)

References:

Ambrus M, Gilissen H K and Van Kempen JJH (2014) Public values in water law: A case of substantive fragmentation? *Utrecht Law Review* 10:8–30

Campbell JL (2002) Ideas, politics, and public policy

Hajer M and Versteeg W (2005) A decade of discourse analysis of environmental politics: Achievements, challenges, perspectives. *J Environ Policy Plan* 7:175-184

Schmidt VA (2001) Discourse and the legitimation of economic and social policy change in Europe. In *Globalization and the European Political Economy*, ed. SWeber, 229–72 New York: Columbia Univ. Press

Van Rijswick M, Edelenbos J, Hellegers P, Kok M and Kuks S (2014) Ten building blocks for sustainable water governance: an integrated method to assess the governance of water. *Water Int* 39:5, 725-742

E2 - Multi-level network potential

The importance of a concise network between different levels and the potential generator of the practice that leads to more efficient results in terms of implementing solutions to achieve a smart water society.

Different levels of interaction: public organisations, private companies, management institutions, water utilities and others.

Flexible and dynamic networks are important, in order to deal with governance challenges with different interests and perspectives, and with stakeholders acting at different levels (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Gupta *et al.*, 2010; Moser and Ekstrom, 2010).

E.2.1. Multi-level network

Interaction with common objectives and sharing responsibilities and resources between the different levels of governance.

Questions:

- What is the level of interaction between the different groups that are linked to water-smartness, such as governments, institutions, and private stakeholders?
- Are there formal meetings where these networks are strengthened?
- Are there other informal mechanisms in place to facilitate contributions from different types of stakeholders?
- To what extent do these interactions bring positive results for the development of a smart society when it comes to water challenges?
- To what extent are goals co-defined and co-implemented among these different groups?
- Is there freedom for developing proposals of alternatives that address challenges regarding to the water sector by different actors?
- Is there a clear attribution of roles that allows for long-term, integrated and sustainable policies/solutions for water challenges?

Scoring:

++	High degree of articulation between the different levels of the network	It generates the creation of a solid body of management with integrated policies, which promote a strong vision of common goals and well-defined sharing of responsibilities. There is autonomy of the parties to create long-term solutions that aim at a sustainable water management.
+	Existence of articulation between the different actors of the network	There is some degree of articulation, but there is a sectorisation of solutions and implementation of measures. The actions generated show a certain degree of connection but, despite the recognition of common goals, there is a limited autonomy to develop solutions towards common goals.
0	Limited articulation between network actors	Although there is some articulation between the different levels, decisions are centralised in certain groups, usually those with greater hierarchical power, as well as they have difficulties in recognizing common goals in the process of building smart water solutions, resulting in inefficient actions that tend to work only in a short-term scope.
-	Low degree of connection between actors and limited sharing of common goals	Little articulation between actors and solutions are generally developed in a top-down scheme. This means that such solutions are not validated by the different actors as there is no autonomy to produce actions that aim to cover the difficulties/interests presented by the whole group. Usually, they are poor articulated solutions that do not fully cover the common challenges of efficient water management.
--	Inexistent Articulation of different actors and no sharing of common goals	There is no recognition of common goals in the search for solutions. It generates actions without any articulation between the different stakeholders, producing solutions that are not very concise and usually last short-term only.

References:

Gupta J, Termeer C, Klostermann J, Meijerink S, Van Den Brink M, Jong P, Nooteboom S and Bergsma E (2010) The Adaptive Capacity Wheel: A method to assess the inherent characteristics of institutions to enable the adaptive capacity of society. *Environ Sci Policy* 13:459-471

Huxham C and Vangen S (2005) *Managing to Collaborate: The theory and Practice of Collaborative Advantage*. New York: Routledge

E.2.2. Cross-sectorial capacity

Level of integration and coordination between different sectors that shares a common topic, in this case, water challenges (Example: Industries, wastewater treatment sector, environment, governance).

Cooperation between different sectors such as wastewater treatment and industry. This assessment criterion is particularly relevant in articulation with C. (Circular Economy) to assess the capacity of stakeholders to engage in new circular business models and create synergies, as well as supports the development of new governance models.

Questions:

- Are there any concerns for cross sectorial need on water policy design?
- Is there articulation in a forum to consolidate agendas and strengthen commitment to address water challenges?
- How far will the ability to cross these different sectors go?
- Which kind of procedures are used to avoid silos in sectorial water management policies?
- Are there strategies and policies to achieve circular economy?
- When intersection between the various sectors exists, is there a clear definition of responsibilities and tasks for water smart solutions implementation?
- Which means exist to foster and ensure coherence between sectoral policies?

Scoring:

++	High degree -of cross sectorial capacity	<p>There is great articulation between sectoral policies, and there is mobilization to reach them in a collaborative process. This involves presence in forums in the search for cross-sector collaboration towards circular economy goals, as well as specific mechanisms to ensure coherence between sectoral policies.</p> <p>These corporations are dynamic and result in fit-for-purpose problem solving necessary to solve complex, multi-level and unknown challenges (taken from the GCF “Clear division of responsibilities” scoring).</p>
+	Some level of cross sectorial capacity	<p>There is articulation between the different sectors with the production of a shared agenda but still linked to the individual sectors. Mobilization in discussion forums to create an agenda that accommodates the different demands.</p>
0	Low degree of engagement for collaboration	<p>There is limited articulation between the sectors, little space for discussion that addresses the different demands, low participation in collaborative forums and limited development of integrative solutions.</p>

-	Low interest in collaborative work by the different sectors	Disarticulation between actors, with solutions being developed based on the sectoral demands. Lack of dialogue between sectors and little space to discuss and negotiate a common approach to tackle water-related challenges. Authorities are fragmented or they lack interest. Moreover, miscommunication and lack of trust are causes that block effective water governance (taken from the GCF “Clear division of responsibilities” scoring).
--	Inexistent collaborative work between the sectors	Each sector is responsible for promoting its own solutions without direct articulation with others. No space for dialogue between the different sectors, which results in the development and implementation of disjointed solutions.

References:

OECD (2011) Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development: Water Governance in OECD Countries: A Multi-level Approach. OECD Studies on Water. Paris, France

OECD (2015) Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development: OECD Principles on Water Governance. OECD Ministerial Council Meeting. Paris, France

E.2.3. Transboundary Cooperation

Transboundary Cooperation refers to stakeholders showing interest, availability, and operational capacity to cooperate beyond boundaries.

This new metric proposed consider that in some LLs (ex. Flanders) there are environmental pressures that require cooperation across administrative and national borders, especially at the river basin level.

Questions:

- Is there willingness and operational capacity for cross-border cooperation on water management?
- Are there open communication channels for discussion to address the challenges of water management between different actors responsible for a certain river basin?
- Are there any commitments like treaties and conventions to promote this cooperation towards a more efficient management across regional and national borders?

Scoring:

++	High operational capacity and willingness to cooperate	Formal commitment for an efficient transboundary cooperation with great operational capacity. Well established communication channels between actors across regional and national borders.
+	Intermediate level of willingness to cooperate	Articulation for cooperation between river basin actors, with availability and interest in the efficient management of water bodies and creation of solutions to address water challenges.
0	Low interest for commitment in building transboundary cooperation	There is cooperation, but little opening for the consolidation of actions that lead to efficient cooperation. Parties show little interest in cooperating and creating solutions that favour management in order to accommodate different regional/territorial demands.
-	Low operational capacity and availability to cooperate	Almost incipient articulation occurring inefficiently for the creation of solutions for the river basin management issues. There is little or no interest in cooperating, promoting low operational capacity and little resolution of issues such as water dispute.
--	No actions for transboundary cooperation	No action of cooperation between the various actors that make up the management of a river basin, causing disputes among users, as well as conflicts of interest between governments.

References:

Koop, S. H. A., Koetsier, L., Doornhof, A., Reinstra, O., Van Leeuwen, C. J., Brouwer, S., Dieperink, C., & Driessen, P. P. J. (2017). Indicators of the water governance Capacity Framework. *Water Resources Management*, 31(11), 3427–3443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-017-1677-7>

Moser SC, Ekstrom JA (2010) A framework to diagnose barriers to climate change adaptation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 107:22026–22031

Pahl-Wostl C (2009) A conceptual framework for analysing adaptive capacity and multi-level learning processes in resource governance regimes. *Glob Environ Chang* 19:354–365

Scott, J. W. (2000). Transboundary cooperation on Germany's Borders: Strategic regionalism through multilevel governance. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 15(1), 143–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08865655.2000.9695545>

Zeitoun, M., & Mirumachi, N. (2008). Transboundary water interaction I: reconsidering conflict and cooperation. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 8(4), 297–316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-008-9083-5>

ANNEX 2 - Preliminary list of metrics relevant for WP5

WATER-SMART SOCIETY												
#	<p>Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation (SO E) to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses (SO A), to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society (SO B), to boost value creation around water (SO C), while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure (SO D).</p>											
B-WaterSmart Assessment framework						Contributors						
<p>The B-WaterSmart framework supports the creation and implementation of strategic plans to achieve the water-smart society vision</p>						<p>WP5 team members: Carla Gomes (ICS-UL); Rosário Oliveira (ICS-UL); Luísa Schmidt (ICS-UL); Marcella Melo (ICS-UL); Margarida Rebelo (LNEC); Clemens Strehl (IWW); Alexandra Schmuck (IWW); Stefania Munaretto (KWR); Sigrid Damman (SINTEF); Sofía Tirado Sarti (UNED)</p>						
Framework structure												
N	Strategic Objective	Soc	Env	Econ	Tech	Gov	Assessment criteria (AC)	Metric short title	Metric description - free text	Indicator	Unit	Data source
1	A. Ensuring water for all relevant uses	+	+	+	+	+	A.1 Safe and secure fit-for-purpose water provision	A.1.1. Fresh water consumption	Water use in households	Total abstraction of fresh water per inhabitant (m ³ per year)	m ³ per year	Eurostat/National Statistics Institutes
								A.1.2. Water quality	Data on supply of treated water	Tested and proper quality water (safe water)	%	Eurostat/National Statistics Institutes

						A.1.3. Water safety	Risk perceptions	Perceived risk of reclaimed wastewater	Likert scale	Municipality/water utility
						A.1.4. Public safety	Flood prevention (infrastructures and measures)	Stormwater retention	Area/capacity	Municipality
						A.1.5. Water security	Water storage and existent reserves, duration/longevity	Water storage capacity	Cubic meter (m3)/population or consumption levels	Water utility
					A.2 Accessibility and equity (for people and for other uses)	A.2.1. Public accessibility (drinking water)	Availability of (drinking)/quality water in public spaces and green areas	Water fountains in public spaces	Number per area	Municipality
						A.2.2. Affordability	Financial mechanisms to relieve costs of water services for households; existence of social tariffs for connecting to the water service and/or for volumes consumed (cf Observ.)	Social tariff	Score 0-2 (no social tariff to connection/service)	Municipality
						A.2.3. Public accessibility (climate and health)	Availability of water in public spaces and green areas for cooling purposes (e.g. in heatwaves)	Area of water bodies accessible to the public (including for leisure)	Area of water/area of green area	Municipality

						A.3 Financial viability	A.3.1. Complaints	Complaints over water tariffs and charges	Complaints over water tariffs and charges	% complaints per nr of users	Water utility/regulation agency
							A.3.2. Cost perceptions	Perception about the costs of treated drinking water	Willingness to pay	Monetary value	Municipality/water utility
							A.3.3. Financial continuation	Financial arrangements to ensure a robust and long-term policy	To what extent do financial arrangements secure long-term, robust policy implementation, continuation, and risk reduction?	5 score +/-	Governance Capacity Framework
2	B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society					B.2 Enhanced ecosystem services to society	B.2.1. Regulating services	Filtration of contaminants/pollution and regulation of natural cycles	Dilution by freshwater and marine ecosystems (CICES 5.1.1.1)		CICES
							B.2.2. Provisioning services	Provision of basic resources which benefit the local population directly	Surface water for drinking (CICES 4.2.1.1)		CICES
							B.2.3. Cultural services	Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions	Recreational activities enjoyed by the local population		CICES

3	C. Boosting value creation around water					+	+	+	C.1 Circular policy making (new name instead of: Decision and policy making)	C.1.1. Green Procurement	Green Public Procurement (GPP) has been used as a proxy for market creation for circular economy products and services	GP criteria applied in public contracts	List of criteria	Policy instruments		
										C.1.2. Plans and strategies	Existence of specific policy instruments (plans, strategies, legislation, regulations) that aim to implement CE principles (water-energy-waste nexus)	Existent policy instruments and regulations related to Circular Economy (CE)	Number	Policy instruments		
										C.5.1. Innovative policy design	Implementation of innovative solutions that follow EC and water-smart principles	Number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials as a proxy for innovation		Eurostat		
										C.5.2. Innovative policy design	Incorporation of recovered raw materials and nutrients into the value chains (waste & water)	Percentage of recovered raw materials/nutrients incorporated into the value chains (waste & water)	%	Environment agencies		
5	E. Engaging citizens /actors in continuous co-learning and innovation							+		++	E.1 Awareness	E.1.1. Public attitudes towards climate change (national context)	Survey-based questions regarding social awareness and attitudes regarding climate change (European Social Survey)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you think world's climate is changing - How much have you thought about climate change before today - Climate change caused by natural processes, human activity, or both - To what extent feel personal responsibility to reduce climate change - How worried about climate change 	4/5-point Likert scales	European Social Survey

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